

RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

Deliverable

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Editor(s)	Konstantinos Nikolopoulos (UDUR)		
Authors (s)	Konstantinos Nikolopoulos (UDUR), Theodoros Mertzimekis (NKUA), Pavlos Krasakis (NTUA)		
Contributor (s)	Eleni Petra, Paraskevi Nomikou, Effie Zafirakopoulou, Stavroula Kazana, Konstantina Bejelou (NKUA), Antonio Pascoal, Pedro Batista, Luis Sebastiao (IST-ID), Emmanuele Coccolo (EVOL), Javier Escartin (ENS), Konstantinos Karantzalos, Valsamis Ntouskos, (NTUA), Angelos Mallios (PLOA).		
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Disclaimer

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RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity gap in sampling and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. These goals will be achieved by combining state-of-the-art methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy. It will also design new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
DB	Database
EIC	European Innovation Council
EU	European Union
F2SS	Forecasting & Foresight Support System
FSS	Forecasting Support Systems
GIS	Geographical Information System
ML	Machine Learning
POIS2ON	Prototype RAMONES Information System for SocioecONomic stakeholders
RMIS	Risk Management Information System
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
WP	Work Package

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Abstract

RAMONES is an ambitious, high-risk FET H2020 project which aims to achieve high-resolution temporal and spatial underwater AI-driven radioactivity measurements, in situ and in near-real-time, forming a game changer in deep-water environmental monitoring. RAMONES proposes a new generation of submarine radiation-sensing instruments, assisted by State of the Art robotic and artificial intelligence solutions towards understanding radiation related risks near and far from coastal areas, while providing data for the international community towards shaping new policies and governance guidelines for environmental sustainability, economic growth, and human health.

In addition, one of the main goals of RAMONES is also to introduce novel monitoring and response channels to **inform key socio-political and socio-economic stakeholders** at regular intervals from medium (hourly, daily, weekly) to low (monthly to inter-annually) periodicity . To this end, the deliverable **5.7. of Work Package 5 provides the latest additions to the prototype information system, POIS2ON** (Prototype RAMONES Information System for Socioeconomic stakeholders) that was delivered in D5.4.

POIS2ON provides statistical and ML forecasts for radionuclide concentrations at high frequency in the sea as well as respective instantaneous risks. At the last stage (deliverable D5.8) full risk awareness capabilities will be integrated into the system. Finally, provision for spatio-temporal representation and visualization will be prescribed via connections to a GIS system (Geographical Information Systems) as well as through links to a system developed by UCA that simulates and calculates absorbed dosages from microorganisms and humans (D5.8).

Keywords

RAMONES; POIS2ON; Radioactivity; Deep Water; Information System; Forecasting; Risk.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context

This document belongs to Work Package 5 (WP5, *Citizen Awareness, Communication and Dissemination Activities*), and in particular to Task T5.2 Raising Awareness / Supporting policymaking [M25-M48] - Lead: UDUR with Participants: NKUA, UCA, ENS within which RAMONES provides the latest version and respective additions to the **POIS2ON** system (D5.1, D5.2, D5.3, D5.4) that has integrated the **RMIS** - (Risk Management Information System) (D5.5, D5.6).

1.2 Structure of the document

This document is organized according to the following structure and contents:

Section 1. Objectives and approach

Section 2. Additions to the prototype POIS2ON system

Section 3. Conclusions and the Future

1.3 Objectives and approach

The objectives of the RAMONES D5.7 deliverable is to deliver the latest version of the prototype system **POIS2ON** with features of the RMIS system. The RMIS system is a subsystem of POIS2ON for calculating and visualizing the Risk Indices. The scope of RMIS is to inform key socio-political and socio-economic stakeholders at regular intervals at medium frequencies (daily, weekly) of evolving risks in sea-areas of interest. A significant component of this deliverable focuses on the integration of Geographical Information System (GIS) capabilities to enhance data visualization, interpretation, and accessibility. GIS functionalities aim to:

- Provide spatio-temporal representation of radioactivity data, enabling users to view dynamic changes over time and space.
- Offer advanced interactive tools for filtering, querying, and analyzing datasets, ensuring stakeholders can explore patterns and trends effectively. Deliver multi-layered maps that integrate external datasets, such as bathymetric information, static active fault traces, and ecosystem features, to provide a holistic environmental context.

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- Facilitate decision-making and policy support through intuitive visualizations, such as heatmaps, 3D renderings, highlighting locations with radioactivity measurements and key environmental insights.
- This approach leverages cutting-edge GIS technology to ensure that POIS2ON not only meets but exceeds the expectations of stakeholders by delivering a robust and user-friendly platform. The GIS functionalities could support analytics and risk management tools, making the system an essential asset for addressing marine radioactivity challenges.

This is a work in progress that started in M18 and will be completed in M48, creating a fully functional prototype information system for public use (D5.8).

2. Additions to the prototype POIS2ON system

There have been four major developments for POIS2ON during the last few months of the RAMONES project, since January 2024:

1. The system was transferred to a secure server operating within NKUA
2. The DB (database of the system) has been amended to allow for a MissionID identifier, so as to be able to allow a graph to capture movement of instruments across the sea – rather than assuming static measurements in the same spot for the duration of a mission,
3. Visuals have been added to support [2.]
4. Data from the online DB (csv type) can now be displayed (eg. maps and graphs) to the external GIS system

The four additions are described in more detail below:

Addition 1:

The actual POIS2ON system developed with R, R shiny, Python, and MySQL, is finally running **securely** in a **server within the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens**, at the address:

<http://195.134.90.204/Pois2on/>

accessed from anywhere in the world. Current access to POIS2ON at the aforementioned address is done with the:

Username: Ramones

Password: Gnikol2907

There is also a series of administrative passwords for the system that are held by UDUR and NKUA. Once real data from the missions of the project are input into the system, new passwords will be issued that will be only available to the consortium and the funders.

Addition 2:

The system database has been amended to allow for a MissionID identifier (and respective Key) so as to be able to allow a graph to capture movement of the instruments within the sea

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at different longitudes, latitudes, and depths respectively –rather than assuming static measurements at the same spot for the duration of a mission. Previously, every graph was referring to a fixed location while now it captures a specified area. Essentially, a mission allows movement of one instrument over time in an area and all this becomes now one unified graph, and one forecast for the system, stored securely in the system DB and visualized respectively.

In Figure 1 we see the new input file (XLS/csv) that allows for different latitudes, longitudes, and depths:

Figure 1 - New input XLS/csv file.

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In Figure 2 we see the forecasting over the new input file. In the specific example, the time series of the activity recorded as the total aggregate of spectra collected during the mission is shown. In addition, a Tab can be clicked to show the respective risk.

Figure 2 - Forecasts for the new input file.

Addition 3:

The particular way to visualize data focuses on the spatial distribution of the activity, while it helps the user to have a better understanding of the studied area. In the example depicted in Figure 3 we see the full screen from top to bottom where the map is also visible; here we can see the location where the measurements took place (automatically via the longitude and latitude information in the XLS/csv file).

Figure 3 - 3D visualisation of the scanned are during the mission.

Addition 4:

The GIS system provides users with several interactive functionalities for monitoring and analyzing radioactivity data, specifically ^{226}Ra , in marine ecosystems. In Figure 4 & 5, maps visualizing measurement points near Kolumbo, Greece, with each point linked to specific timestamps, allowing users to navigate and zoom in/out on the map. A legend on the map indicates ^{226}Ra concentration levels using bubble sizes and a color gradient, helping users quickly interpret spatial distribution. In the left part of the dashboard, two gauge indicators display the sum of measurement points (currently 54 out of 100) and the concentration of ^{226}Ra .

Additionally, the dashboard includes a 3D visualization that shows data over time, represented by vertical bars whose height corresponds to the intensity or concentration of measurements. The user has the ability to choose between two sensors (aSPECT & GASPAR) and can use standard tools, such as zooming, panning, and layer control, filters are also available, in order to navigate the surrounding area between 2D and 3D views

It is important to note that Geographical Information Systems (GIS) are powerful tools for the study and monitoring of marine environments by enabling the integration and interpretation of diverse datasets from various sources, such as multibeam bathymetry, side-scan sonar, seismic profiles, and in situ explorations, to generate detailed morphological and geospatial analyses. GIS is particularly valuable due to the unique challenges and complexities of monitoring vast and dynamic underwater ecosystems (Wright & Scholz, 2005; ESRI, 2024).

So, in Figures 4, 5 and 6 we see the visualization realized in the external GIS after data has been transferred from POIS2ON to the GIS (with a predetermined format) for the same input file as in Figure 1, that was forecasted in Figure 2.

Figure 4 - External GIS visualisation with data provided from POIS2ON – part I.

Figure 5 - External GIS visualisation with data provided from POIS2ON – part II.

Figure 6 - The external GIS visualization in the 3D scene displays surrounding environmental entities, such as active fault traces (blue lines) from the National Observatory of Athens (NOA) and the world's seafloor geomorphological features (colored polygons).

3. Conclusions and the Future

RAMONES aspires to introduce novel monitoring and response channels to inform key socio-political and socio-economics stakeholders at regular intervals. For this purpose, the deliverable D5.7 of Work Package 5 provides the latest additions to the prototype information system POIS2ON with integrated capabilities from the RMIS.

POIS2ON provides statistical and ML forecasts for radionuclide concentrations in the sea, as well as respective instantaneous risks. Provision for spatio-temporal representation and visualization have been implemented via connections to a GIS system as well as references to a system developed by UCA that simulates and calculates absorbed dosages from microorganisms and humans (D5.8).

Next Steps

For the next steps, we plan in D5.8 to integrate fully Risk Management facilities, provide a direct link to the UCA software, receive information from the GIS and visualize it within POIS2ON, providing the final version of the system for public use.

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